

SOCIAL SCIENCES

TO THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF THE SHAHRUKHIYA SETTLEMENT (ARCHAEOBOTANY AND PLACES OF WORSHIP)

Bogomolov G.

*Senior Research Fellow (PhD), Institute of Anthropology
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Pak L.

*Senior Research Fellow (PhD), Institute of Anthropology
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Shadmanova A.

*Junior researcher, Institute of Anthropology
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Abstract

The focus of this study is on Shahrukhiya settlement through the lens of archaeobotanical materials and sacred sites. The analysis of plant remains identified during archaeological excavations enables the reconstruction of not only population's nutritional habits and agricultural production systems, but also the way humans engaged with the environment during the medieval period. Particular attention is paid to the study of sacred places and places of worship located on the territory of the settlement and its surroundings. The socio-anthropological study of these places makes it possible to identify the characteristic features of the religious life of the local population, trace the synthesis and development of pre-Islamic and Islamic traditions, and determine the role of sacred spaces in shaping the cultural landscape of the region. A comprehensive approach, combining archaeobotanical, socio-cultural data contributes to a more complete understanding of the development of Shahrukhiya settlement as a major medieval center of Central Asia, as well as reveals the relationship between economic activity and the spiritual culture of its inhabitants.

Keywords: Shahrukhiya archaeological site, Central Asia, medieval city, sociocultural anthropology, archaeobotany, sacred places, ritual practices, cultivated plants, cereal crops, weed flora.

The archaeology of medieval cities in Central Asia has long remained an “archaeology of elites”, focusing primarily on fortifications, monumental architecture, ornaments, and numismatic materials, while the plant component of their cultural layers received comparatively little scholarly attention. The development of archaeobotany has unexpectedly shifted focus to some of the most fundamental aspects of past societies: what people ate, which crops they cultivated, which kinds of herbal plants were employed for the treatment, and how they coped with droughts and crop failures. By employing archaeobotanics, scientists obtained insights into the “invisible” urban life - the everyday practices and subsistence strategies of ordinary people. At the same time, archaeobotanical evidence can shed light not only on economic activities and daily life but also on the ritual and religious practices of local communities.

A particularly illustrative example combining archaeobotanics and sociocultural anthropology is provided by the archaeological site of Shahrukhiya, which constitutes a unique case study for investigating the interaction between plants, people, and cultural practices in medieval Central Asia.

Methods

The study employs retrospective, historical, and comparative methods of analysis.

Discussion

There was once an amazing city on the territory of the modern Akkurgan district⁶. In eastern written

sources it is known as Benaket. During the X–XIIth centuries, it was one of the most prosperous and beautiful urban settlements of the Tashkent Oasis. However, at the beginning of the XIIIth century, the city was completely devastated during the Mongol invasion (Bartold, 1963, p. 484).

This archaeological site has been mentioned repeatedly in medieval itineraries, geographical essays, and historical chronicles. It is located approximately 80 km southwest of Tashkent, on the elevated right bank of the Syr Darya river near the confluence of the Karasu channel, one of the ancient branches of the Akhangaran river. The site represents the ruins of one of the largest urban centers of the Tashkent Oasis. For several centuries, the city functioned as an important military, commercial, and economic center closely linked to the caravan trade. The settlement survived until the early eighteenth century and is identified with Benaket - Shahrukhiya (Buryakov and Bogomolov, 2009, pp. 82–84). Therefore, Benaket-Shahrukhiya-Sharqiya are all names of the same settlement.

According to historical sources, during the 1370s–1390s Amir Timur, having consolidated his rule over Transoxiana, initiated the reconstruction of cities and settlements destroyed by the Mongols, as well as building new fortresses. (Buryakov, 1983, p. 62; Alimov, 2005, p. 22).

From the earliest accounts, the city was surrounded by legends and incredible rumors. One of the

⁶ Akkurgan district is an administrative district of Tashkent Region, Uzbekistan

legends says that the city was so densely built that the goat jumped onto the roof of one house reached Toytepa⁷ without touching the ground. According to local belief, the place where the goat first landed later became a sacred site known as Shamorkari-Avliya (modern Shamirkori Avliyo), accompanied by a sacred grove.

Another legend tells of a prolonged siege by countless armies of invaders. The city appeared on the verge of collapse: siege engines had breached the walls, fires raged within the settlement, yet the defenders continued to resist, pouring boiling pitch upon the attackers and showering them with stones and arrows. Suddenly, all ceased. No defenders were visible on the walls. The invaders broke through the gates and entered the city, but it was empty; no one was there. Reaching the banks of the Syr Darya, they witnessed the last defenders disappearing into underground passages beneath the riverbank. According to legend, anyone who attempted to follow them never returned. These underground tunnels are said to extend for great distances, even passing beneath the Syr Darya itself. Such underground labyrinths do indeed exist and form a complex network beneath the city. Early investigators attempted to trace their routes. Other legends say that the labyrinths and caves were dug by tigers or tell of immense treasures hidden by the townspeople and submerged in the river during times of danger. A further cycle of legends is associated with a sacred place and elm grove located on the northern outskirts of the site.

Some researchers argue that the original name of the early city remains unknown. However, turkic sources from the period of the Turkic Khaganate mention a locality called Kangu Tarband, identified as a frontier point of the khaganate. It is possible that this reference pertains to the present site. At that time, the Syr Darya was also known as the Kang River, while tarband meant “crossing” or “passage.” Thus, Kangu Tarband may be interpreted as “the crossing over the Kang River.” The later name Benaket may derive from a transformation of this term, appearing in early Arabic itineraries and geographical essays, where ben represents a shortened form of tarband (“crossing”) and ket means “city.”

Another group of researchers associates the name of Shahrukhiya with Shahrukh, the son of Amir Timur. According to historical accounts, in 1392 Amir Timur, returning from a military campaign, recognized the strategic importance of the location, restored the city, and granted it to his youngest son Shahrukh. Consequently, the settlement became known as Shahrukh-shahr (“the city of Shahrukh”), later evolving into Shahrukhiya.

Subsequently, when the city came under Shaybanid rule, it was also referred to as Sharqiya (“Eastern”) (Kastan’ev, 1913; Buryakov, 1978, p. 11).

The Syr Darya delta was characterized by plant communities typical of Central Asian riverine ecosystems, including moisture-loving trees and shrubs. Its flora included such species as cattail (*Typha*), reed (*Phragmites*), sedge (*Carex*), willow (*Salix*), poplar (*Populus*), and Turanga poplar (*Populus diversifolia*), meadow vegetation and grasses. All of them remain widespread in the region today.

Weed plants are commonly encountered in archaeological deposits together with cultivated cereals, indicating a greater role for artificial irrigation. Among the most common weeds identified in the archaeobotanical assemblage are amaranth (*Amaranthus* sp.), lamb’s quarters (*Chenopodium album*), barnyard grass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), millet (*Panicum* sp.), sedges (*Carex* sp.), reed grass (*Phragmites australis*), and narrow-leaved cattail (*Typha angustifolia*). This reflects the intensity of agricultural exploitation: the more intensively croplands and pastures were utilized, the greater the proportion of ruderal flora.

The study revealed a significant archaeobotanical assemblage consisting primarily of cereal crops, which formed the basis of the diet and constituted a key element of food security. Legumes, oil-crops, nuts, fruits, and grape were also identified, indicating a highly developed horticultural and possibly viticultural tradition. However, most of the recovered plant remains consisted of carbonized grains of bread cereals represented by two principal species: barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), whose abundance confirms their leading role in the local economy.

Pic. 1 Carbonized barley grains from Shahrukhiya settlement

⁷Toytepa is one of the major districts (administrative centers) of Tashkent Region, Uzbekistan.

Pic. 2 Carbonized wheat grains from Shahrukhiya settlement

The significance of barley alongside wheat is further supported by several characteristics of this crop. These include its high tolerance to arid conditions, its ability to grow on poor soils, and its earlier maturation compared to most other cereals. Furthermore, barley served as an important fodder crop for animals. The importance of barley, alongside wheat,

The legume assemblage is represented primarily by lentil (*Lens culinaris*) and *Vicia sativa* L., the latter is a weed contaminating lentil fields.

Analysis of the weed spectrum revealed the presence of white goosefoot (*Chenopodium album*) and amaranth (*Amaranthus* sp.). Representatives of the genus *Chenopodium* are the most abundant category of archaeobotanical remains among ruderal and meadow plants and have been identified at the overwhelming majority of archaeological sites across Central Asia (Spengler, Maksudov, F., et al. 2018; Spengler, R. N. 2019, p.215-227).

Pic.3 Seed of lamb's quarters (*Chenopodium album*) from Shahrukhiya settlement.

(*Chenopodium album* is an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the family *Amaranthaceae* and is commonly classified as a ruderal species)

It should be noted that ash pits, hearths, and *badrabs* (refuse pits) are among the most promising contexts for archaeobotanical sampling. Such contexts are often associated with ritual activities at ancient settlements. Most plant remains are preserved primarily in a carbonized form.

Fruit and legume remains are frequently discovered in the vicinity of religious sites, including mosques and mazars (Islamic shrines). This allows them to be interpreted as possible components of ritual offerings, in which the fruits of the earth symbolized gratitude for a good harvest. Consequently, the presence of such remains in sacred contexts suggests that part of agricultural production may have been used not only for subsistence purposes but also in religious ceremonies, reflecting the close interconnection between economic and spiritual spheres of life in the medieval city. One of the most vivid examples of such a sacred context is the site of Shamorkori Avliya.

In late May 1913, Collegiate Assessor I. A. Kastanye was travelling under the scorching sun in a cart hired in Yanaqurghan, eagerly anticipating his first encounter with the ruins of Shahrukhiya. Suddenly, to his

astonishment, he beheld what appeared almost miraculous - a mirage amidst the barren landscape covered with sparse vegetation. Rising unexpectedly was a sacred grove of ancient elm trees (karagach), visible from several versts away. As he approached Shahrukhiya, the structures of the sacred place gradually came into view, enclosed, like the grove itself, by a mud-brick wall. Large stork nests were visible in the trees. Adjacent to the grove stood the ruins of the Mosque of Abdullah Khan (the most of its walls had already collapsed, leaving only a small section with an arch intact by then. Near the mosque ruins was a low, single-chambered mazar constructed of fired brick. It was adorned with animal horns, strips of cloth, and horse tails (bunchuk). All these features were surrounded by large shade-giving trees forming part of the sacred grove known as Shamorkori Avliyo or Shamar-kara-Auliyo (Kastan'e, 1913).

Among the local population, including inhabitants of more distant areas, the locality of Sharkiya remains well known owing to the mazar of Shamorkori Avliyo and its sacred grove. Pilgrims undertaking ziyarat visit the site not only from neighbouring settlements but also from other regions of Uzbekistan (Jizzakh, Zaamin, Parkent, and Pskent), as well as from southern Kazakhstan (Sairam and Shymkent) and Khujand.

Pic. 4 Shamorkori Avliyo. The Sacred Grove

It is therefore unsurprising that numerous legends have developed around the mazar of Shamorkori Avliyo. According to one tradition, the site—comprising both the mazar and the grove—received its name from two saints who sacrificed a ram or goat there (according to I. A. Kastan’*e*), while the animal itself subsequently acquired sacred status. The trees of the grove were believed to have sprung from the blood of the sacrificial animal scattered upon the ground. Significantly, until relatively recently, when animals—particularly roosters or hens—were sacrificed, their blood was deliberately poured onto the roots of a tree or into a hollow within its trunk. Ritual practices performed at the shrine were relatively simple and characteristic of Central Asian *ziyarat* traditions: circumambulation of the sacred space, petitions addressed to the saint, prayers and blessings at the mazar, animal sacrifice (typically a ram or rooster), followed by the preparation of pilaf and, less frequently, *shurpa*. Some pilgrims also lit candles along the pathway leading to the shrine entrance.

In the 1980s and 1990s, the shrine frequently attracted people seeking healing, particularly women suffering from infertility. While the full cycle of *ziyarat* rituals was performed, in some cases the blood of the sacrificial animal—most often a bird, such as a white or red rooster or a white hen—was applied to the face, breasts, and abdomen of the afflicted woman. Children’s faces were likewise anointed with the sacrificial blood. In certain instances, particularly in cases of skin diseases or when an individual was believed to be affected by sorcery or the evil eye, a black hen was offered as a sacrifice.

Notably, Shamirkori Avliyo is regarded as the senior saint among the avliyo of the region. Numerous elements of the associated legends point to a more ancient, pre-Islamic foundation of his cult. These include his manifestation in the form of a serpent or a white goat, his command over wild animals, and his possession of sacred powers connected with both the underworld and the granting of health and fertility. Even his present name, Sho-Mir-Kori, appears to represent a later reinterpretation of the earlier designation Shamor (“wind”). This suggests that the veneration of a wind

deity and related beliefs may once have been widespread among the populations inhabiting the Syr Darya basin.

Speaking of plant assemblages from cultic complexes, it is possible to identify a group of plants that were not typically associated with everyday consumption, suggesting instead their ritual significance, either as offerings or as components of ceremonial practices. Plant remains recovered from the mosque and mazars include species that are absent from domestic deposits, such as fragments of floral bouquets. Certain plant remains demonstrate a clear distinction between domestic and ritual use. Grapes, for example, in domestic areas are usually represented mainly by crushed seeds, whereas in cultic contexts—presumably associated with offerings—whole bunches or intact seeds are found. Similarly, cereal crops are commonly found in residential areas in the form of threshed grains, while sacred contexts contain complete ears of wheat, *harmala* (*Peganum harmala*) (Pak, pp. 55-56), or unprocessed wheat grains. This implies that the same plant species could fulfill both utilitarian and ritual functions depending on the archaeological context.

A complex of ritual plants has also been identified, including juniper, pistachio, cannabis, cereal crops, and fruits. These remains may reflect a variety of ceremonial practices, in which aromatic plants were likely used for rituals of incense burning, whereas fruits and cereals probably served as offerings.

Conclusion

The research of Shahrukhiya settlement is a crucial aspect of studying Central Asia’s historical and cultural heritage. An analysis of the history of archaeological research demonstrates that Shahrukhiya was a significant political, economic, and cultural center of the region, whose development reflected key processes in medieval history. Archaeobotanical data are especially valuable for the reconstruction of the settlement’s past. The analysis of plant remains enables the reconstruction of local economic activities, agricultural organization, irrigation systems, dietary practices, and the relationship between humans and their surroundings. Archaeobotanical materials indicates a well-developed

agricultural system and the efficient use of natural resources, which ensured the long-term sustainability of the urban center. Equally important is the study of sacred sites associated with Shahrukhiya and its surrounding territory. Cult structures, mausoleums, and pilgrimage places reflect the spiritual life of the local population, religious beliefs, and the processes of sacral landscape formation. Investigation of these structures provides deeper insight into the interrelations between the urban environment, religious practices, and the cultural memory of local communities. Thus, an integrated analysis of archaeological, archaeobotanical, and historical-religious data significantly expands our understanding of Shahrukhiya's role in the history of the region. A multidisciplinary approach enables a more comprehensive reconstruction of the natural, economic, and spiritual environment of the medieval city, while also emphasizing the need for further research and preservation of this unique cultural heritage site.

References

1. Alimov, U. (2005). Shokhrukhiya noyob topilmalari. *Moziydan Sado*, 1, 22–25.
2. Arkheologicheskie issledovaniya na gorodishche Shakhrukhiya [Archaeological investigations at the Shakhrukhiya settlement]. (2004). In *Ezhegodnyi sbornik rezul'tatov arkheologicheskikh rabot za proshedshii polevoi sezon* (Vol. 4). O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi.
3. Bartold, V. V. (1963). *Turkestan v epokhu mongol'skogo nashestviya* (Vol. 1). Izdatel'stvo vostochnoy literatury.
4. Buryakov, Yu. F., & Bogomolov, G. I. (2009). Gorodishche Sharkiya. In *Arkheologiya Uzbekistana* (pp. 82–84). Fan.
5. Buryakov, Yu. F. (1983). Arkheologicheskie materialy k topografii Shakhrukhiy XIII–XVIII vv. In *Srednevekovaya gorodskaya kul'tura Kazakhstana i Srednei Azii* (pp. 62–75). Nauka KazSSR.
6. Buryakov, Yu. F. (1990). Rabady srednevekovogo Binaketa. *Istoriya Material'noy Kul'tury Uzbekistana*, 24, 48–63.
7. Gorshunova, O. V. (2008). Svyashchennye derev'ya khoji-barora: Fitolatriya i kul't zhen'skogo bozhestva v Sredney Azii. *Etnograficheskoe Obozrenie*, 1, 71–75.
8. Kastan'e, I. A. (1913). *Otchet o poezdke v Shakhrokhiyu i mestnost' "Kanka"* [Report on a trip to Shakhrokhiya and the locality "Kanka"]. Tashkent.
9. Pak, L. (2025). Archaeology and ethnography in the study of medicinal plants: The case of the harmala. *The Scientific Heritage*, 173, 55–56.
10. Spengler, R. N., Maksudov, F., Bullion, E., Merkle, A., Hermes, T., & [остальные авторы]. (2018). Arboreal crops on the medieval Silk Road: Archaeobotanical studies at Tashbulak. *PLOS ONE*, 13(9), e0204582. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0204582>
11. Spengler, R. N. (2019). Dung burning in the archaeobotanical record of West Asia: Where are we now? *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, 28(2), 215–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00334-018-0669-8>